

more than the local modern improved variety Nanjing 11 and hybrid Nanyou 6.

BG90-2 has high, stable BB resistance, and is a source of BB resistance in breed-

ing programs. It is one of 12 best resistant sources among 10,688 accessions screened by the Plant Protection Institute of the Guangdong Provincial Academy of

Agricultural Sciences. BG90-2 also has good morphoagronomic characters (see table). □

New sources of resistance to major rice diseases

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We evaluated 46 rice varieties at TNAU, Coimbatore, for reaction to brown spot (BS), bacterial blight (BB), and sheath rot (ShR) under artificial screening conditions using the Standard Evaluation

System for Rice. AS18699 and AS19703 had multiple disease resistance (see table). □

Reaction of rice varieties to BS, BB, and ShR, Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a		
	BS	BB	ShR (% infection)
AS688	5	5	2
AS6520	3	3	10
AS18696	5	3	NT
AS18699	3	3	9
AS19103	3	3	2
AS19789	5	5	4
AS19903	5	3	NT
AS22954	3	5	NT
AS23598	5	3	15
AS23972	3	5	7

^a 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible; NT = not tested.

Reaction of IR varieties to rice yellow dwarf (RYD)

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Reactions of 26 IR varieties to RYD infection were tested in the greenhouse. Newly emerged *Nephotettix virescens* nymphs had 25-d acquisition access on RYD-infected TN1 plants. Six-day-old seedlings were confined with 2 viruliferous insects per seedling in test tubes for 1 d. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted in clay pots, kept in screened trays, and scored 40-60 d after inoculation. Percentage infection of IR varieties was 20-76%. TN1 was 97% infected. Six IR varieties had RYD infection lower than 30% and were considered resistant (see table). □

Reaction of ASD varieties to various rice diseases

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In 1983-84, 15 rice varieties released by the Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamudram, were screened for disease resistance by artificial inoculation in the greenhouse at TNAU. Varieties were evaluated for resistance to brown spot (BS), bacterial blight (BB), sheath rot (ShR), blast (BI), and rice tungro virus (RTV) using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES). ASD5 and ASD11 had multiple disease resistance (see table). □

Disease resistance of ASD varieties, Coimbatore, India.^a

Variety	Disease rating ^a				
	BI	BS	BB	RTV	ShR
ASD1	3	5	5	5	5
ASD2	3	5	5	5	3
ASD3	3	5	7	5	3
ASD4	5	5	7	5	3
ASD5	3	3	3	1	3
ASD6	3	5	3	5	3
ASD7	5	3	5	5	3
ASD8	5	5	5	5	5
ASD9	5	3	5	3	3
ASD10	5	5	5	3	5
ASD11	3	3	3	3	3
ASD12	3	5	5	3	3
ASD13	NT	3	3	NT	NT
ASD14	7	3	5	3	5
ASD15	7	5	7	5	5

^a By the 1980 SES scale: 0-3 = resistant, 5 = moderate, 7 = susceptible, 9 = highly susceptible, NT = not tested.

IR varieties with low percentages of RYD infection, IIRRI, 1984.

Variety	Total tested ^a (no.)	Plants infected (%)
IR7	108	20
IR24	104	24
IR26	102	24
IR29	104	25
IR30	100	27
IR43	107	21
TN1 (check)	95	97

^a Based on 6 trials, each involving 20 seedlings/variety.

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

INSECT RESISTANCE

Behavior of two green leafhopper (GLH) colonies on three rice varieties

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We sought to determine if selection of a GLH *Nephotettix virescens* biotype on a variety with a major gene for resistance results in cross adaptation to another variety with the same major resistance gene.

The response of two GLH colonies—one from susceptible TN1 and selected on moderately resistant TAPL #796 for 18 generations, and another reared on TN1 for at least 100 generations—was determined based on survival, develop-

ment period, and growth index on varieties TAPL #796, IR36, and TN1. TAPL #796 and IR36 have the *Glh* 6 gene for resistance.

Thirty-day-old potted plants of the test varieties were enclosed with 10- × 90-cm mylar film cages and arranged in a randomized complete block design on a water tray in the greenhouse. Each variety was replicated 10 times with 1 pot equaling 1 replication.

Plants in each cage were infested with 10 first-instar GLH nymphs from the respective colonies and regularly observed for the emergence of adults. When adults emerged, the date was recorded and the insects were counted and removed from the cage once a day until adult emergence was complete. The total number of adults that emerged from each cage was determined and percentage survival was computed as

$$\frac{\text{number of adults that emerged}}{\text{number of nymphs infested}} \times 100$$

The mean developmental period (1st instar to adult) on each variety was calcu-

Survival, development period, and growth index of 2 GLH colonies on 3 rice varieties,^a IRRI.

Variety	Survival (%)		Development period (d)		Growth index	
	TAPL #796	TN1	TAPL #796	TN1	TAPL #796	TN1
TAPL #796	90.0 ab	50 c	15.5 c	20.0 a	5.80 a	2.57 b
IR36	57.5 bc	74 abc	17.5 b	19.9 a	3.27 b	3.73 b
TN1	88.0 ab	100 a	14 c	15.8 c	6.04 a	6.12 a

^aUnder each parameter, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

lated and the growth index was computed as

$$\frac{\% \text{ survival}}{\text{mean development period (d)}}$$

Survival of the TAPL #796 was significantly higher than that of the TN1 colony on TAPL #796 (see table). There was no significant difference between the two colonies on IR36 and TN1, and survival of the TAPL #796 colony on TAPL #796 and IR36 did not differ significantly. Development of the TAPL #796 colony was significantly shorter than that of the TN1 colony on TAPL #796 and IR36, but no difference was observed on TN1. The growth index of the colonies significantly

differed only on TAPL #796. The growth index of the TAPL #796 colony was significantly higher on TAPL #796 than on IR36.

The results indicate a degree of insect adaptation to TAPL #796 after 18 generations on the variety. Although TAPL #796 and IR36 have the same gene for GLH resistance, these varieties may have different levels of resistance to the insect or may possess minor genes, which result in little cross adaptation, as indicated by the differences in the reaction of the TAPL #796 colony. □

A new brown planthopper (BPH) resistant rice for Pondicherry, India

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Land in the Union Territory, Pondicherry, is intensively cropped with a rice-based multiple cropping system, which has increased pest problems. BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* is a major pest from Jun to Sep, and causes 30-40% damage to the rice crop. Recommended controls have not solved the problem. Almost all varieties grown are highly susceptible to BPH.

We identified BPHR-5 (IR13427-45-2) as having BPH resistance and good yield potential. BPHR-5 is a multiple cross of IR3403-267, IR36, and Ptb 33, and is rated 3 for BPH resistance, based on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES).

BPHR-5 is a medium-dwarf, 95-cm-tall variety. Tillers are semierect, compact, and lodging resistant. It matures in 115-

Table 1. BPH resistance and yield potentials of BPHR-5 in Pondicherry, India.

Site	Yield (t/ha)				Resistance to BPH ^a			
	BPHR-5	IR50	Vaigai	PY2	BPHR-5	IR50	Vaigai	PY2
Lawspet	5.8	—	—	2.1	3	9	9	5
Adingapattu	5.9	—	4.7	—	1	—	3	—
T. N. Palayam	6.8	5.4	—	5.5	1	3	—	3
Mettupalayam	5.1	—	4.5	5.0	3	—	3	3
KVK Farm	5.2	3.7	1.1	4.5	1	5	7	3

^aBy the 1980 SES scale.

120 d when transplanted and grows well in navarai and sornavari seasons. The boot leaf is slightly broad and semierect with late senescence. Grains are coarse, long-slender, with a 5.28 length-breadth ratio. They are opaque white and 1,000 weight is 25 g. BPHR-5 yields 4.8 t/ha in farmer fields and produces better than other varieties tested (Table 1, 2). In one area with heavy BPH pressure, BPHR-5 yielded 5.8 t/ha versus 0.0 for Vaigai and 0.2 for PY2.

After performance trials, BPHR-5 was approved for release as BPH-resistant variety Pondicherry 3 (PY3) by the State Seed Subcommittee of Pondicherry. □

Table 2. Mean yield of BPHR-5 in outstation trials, Pondicherry, India.

Site	Yield (t/ha)	
	BPHR-5	Vaigai
Bhavanisagar	7.3	5.7
Ambasamudram	4.6	4.6
Paiyur	4.2	4.1
Perumangudi	6.8	—
Vilangudi	7.5	—
Viswanathapuram	6.7	—

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